

Appendix A: Supplementary Material

Appendix A.1: Additional GCS reconstructions

Figures [A.1](#)–[A.6](#) show the GCS reconstructions for CME events from rotation #1 and #2. The GCS is outlined on simultaneously matching the outer front of the CME flux rope part as observed in STEREO-A, SOHO, and Solar Orbiter (Metis VLD610; whenever available) white-light images at roughly the same time. For each event several time steps were chosen to perform GCS from which a height-time plot is given. Using a linear fit, the speed of the CME is derived with error estimates taken from the statistical study by Verbeke et al. 2023 (Advances in Space Research, 72, pp. 5243–5262).

Appendix A.2: In-situ measurements - zoom-in

Figure [A.7](#) shows in detail the region around the SBC. The SBC is identified by a strong drop in the total magnetic field, together with a change in the polarity for the B_x (positive to negative) and B_y (positive to negative) component. Plasma- β and density show a clear short-duration peak (spike) at the same time. These criteria hold for both rotations (rotation #1 - left panel; rotation #2 - right panel). In addition we indicate the start of the ripples after. Labels given in Figure [A.7](#) are the same as for Figure 5.

Appendix A.3: Detailed Summary Table

Table [A.1](#) gives a summary of the GCS parameters derived for each CME (see Figures 3 and 4 as well as Figures [A.1](#) to [A.6](#)). From the GCS results we identified events which are most likely related to in-situ signatures, i.e., CME1.4, CME2.2 and CME2.4+5. For these CMEs we performed 3D DBM runs to assess arrival time and speed for better linking and interpretation of the in-situ signatures. As input for the 3D DBM runs we use the results from GCS for CME2.2 and CME2.4+5 and tweaked the results from GCS for CME1.4 such to come from a glancing blow to a flank hit. The optimum values for the interaction events produces an arrival which is roughly 10 hours later than observed. We are able to find a set of parameters within the GCS errors that produce the observed signatures in-situ.

Appendix B: 3D DBM modeling of the CME-CME interaction

3D DBM tracks the kinematics of the infinitesimally thin leading edge of the CME. The interaction of two CMEs in 3D DBM can therefore be approximated as a trailing front encountering the leading front. We note that in reality this is not the case, because the front of the trailing CME first interacts with the back of the leading CME. Nevertheless, this approach offers a simple and fast way to treat CME-CME interactions with 3D DBM. We consider the point where the kinematic curves of two CMEs cross as the interaction point. We assume that during the interaction impulse and mass are conserved and that after the interaction the two CMEs move on as a single entity. The initial parameters are then recalculated for the entity at the interaction point (starting time, starting distance, speed based on conserved momentum, γ parameter), with the solar wind speed slightly enhanced. The γ parameter is recalculated based on the increased CME leading front cross sectional area and mass (for details see [Guo et al.](#)

[2018](#); [Dumbović et al. 2019](#)):

$$\gamma_{1+2} = \frac{\gamma_1 + \frac{M_1}{M_2} \sin^2 \omega_{1+2}}{\left(\frac{M_1}{M_2} + 1\right) \sin^2 \omega_1}, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where γ_1 is the original γ parameter of the first CME, $\frac{M_1}{M_2}$ is the mass ratio of the two CMEs (estimated roughly by the observer, based on the impulsiveness, brightness and spatial extent of the two CMEs in the white light observations), ω_1 is the spatial extent of the first CME (estimated as the extent in either equatorial or meridional plane, whichever is larger) and ω_{1+2} is the extent of the merged CME entity, which is derived by combining the extents of both CMEs in equatorial and meridional planes and choosing whichever is larger. The extent (half-width) of the entity in equatorial plane is calculated as:

$$\omega_{1+2} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}(\omega_{\max} + lon_{\max} - lon_{\min} + \omega_{\min}), \\ \text{when } lon_{\max} - \omega_{\max} > lon_{\min} - \omega_{\min} \\ \omega_{\max}, \text{ otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where ω stands for half-width, lon for longitude and indices max and min correspond to wider and narrower CME in the interaction, respectively. An analogous equation is used to calculate the half-width of the entity in the meridional plane.

The original drag parameters corresponding to CMEs before interaction are calculated according to [Cargill \(2004\)](#) and [Vršnak et al. \(2014\)](#) as:

$$\gamma = \frac{2}{\pi} \frac{1}{\left(\frac{n}{n_{sw}} + \frac{1}{2}\right)} \frac{C_d}{r}, \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where we assume C_d equals 1, r is the radius of the CME, which has toroidal geometry and is calculated according to [Thernisien \(2011\)](#). The density ratio n/n_{sw} is estimated based on the CME speed, using the CME mass vs. speed relation (see Table 1 in [Dissauer et al. 2019](#)) and typical values for density ratio used in the ENLIL cone model (see e.g., [Yordanova et al. 2024](#)), grouping CMEs into three classes: slow (<750 km/s), intermediate (750–1500 km/s) and fast (>1500 km/s). For intermediate CMEs we use density ratio 4 (typical value used in ENLIL cone). For slow and fast CMEs with masses ≈ 2 times smaller and 1.5 times larger than for intermediate CMEs, respectively, we use density ratios of 2 and 6, respectively.

Fig. A.1. CME1.1: Multi-perspective white-light CME signatures (LASCO C2/C3, COR2, Metis), GCS reconstruction shown for a 3D height of 10.8Rs, and kinematics. From the height-time plot the speed is derived using a linear fit (given in the legend).

Fig. A.2. Same as Figure [A.1](#) but for CME1.3. GCS reconstruction is shown for a 3D height of 6.5Rs.

Fig. A.3. Same as Figure [A.1](#) but for CME1.4. GCS reconstruction is shown for a 3D height of 9.4Rs.

Fig. A.4. Same as Figure [A.1](#) but for CME2.1. GCS reconstruction is shown for a 3D height of 13.8Rs.

Fig. A.5. Same as Figure A.1 but for CME2.2. GCS reconstruction is shown for a 3D height of 6.6Rs. We note that we further constrain the GCS reconstruction by taking the low coronal signatures (see Figure 2) into account.

Fig. A.6. Same as Figure A.1 but for CME2.4+5. GCS reconstruction is shown for a 3D height of 13.6Rs. We note that due to the almost spherical appearance we cannot give a strong constraint on the tilt.

Fig. A.7. Zoom-in of Figure 5. See description and legend in Figure 5.

Table A.1. CME hit/miss statistics with GCS parameters derived for each CME and 3D DBM runs performed for those CMEs that likely hit Earth.

GCS params.	CME1.1	CME1.2	CME1.3	CME1.4 Results from GCS		CME2.1	CME2.2	CME2.3	CME2.4+5
Half angle [°]	14	15	5	30	15	15	20	15	44
k [rad]	0.35	0.25	0.14	0.24	0.25	0.35	0.35	0.31	0.94
latitude [°]	-55	50	6	29	-40	-1	-1	43	-23
longitude [°]	3	322	35	0	23	330	330	312	3
tilt [°]	60	40	25	-20	60	-40	-40	-61	-35
Time@21.5 Rs	Nov-01 03:50	Nov-02 09:42	Nov-03 09:09	Nov-03 08:00	Nov-27 12:54	Nov-28 02:33	Nov-28 02:33	Nov-28 03:14	Nov-29 02:18
speed [km/s]	651±32	629±31	352±18	1187±59	552±28	518±26	518±26	1020±51	637±32
hit/miss	miss	miss	miss	gla.-blow	miss	hit	hit	miss	hit
Errors for GCS parameters									
Half angle [°]	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
k [rad]	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
latitude [°]	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
longitude [°]	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
tilt [°]	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
GCS parameters used for 3D DBM to simulate a best hit scenario within errors									
Half angle [°]	24	25	15	40	25	30	30	25	54
k [rad]	0.45	0.35	0.24	0.34	0.35	0.45	0.45	0.41	0.99*
latitude [°]	-49	44	0	23	-34	-1*	-1*	37	-17
longitude [°]	3*	333	24	0*	12	341	341	323	3*
tilt [°]	85	15	0	-45	85	-15	-15	-61	-60
hit/miss	gla.-blow	miss	flank hit	full hit	flank hit	hit	hit	miss	hit
GCS parameters used for 3D DBM to simulate a worst hit scenario within errors									
Half angle [°]	4	5	5*	20	5	10	10	5	34
k [rad]	0.25	0.15	0.1*	0.14	0.15	0.25	0.25	0.21	0.84
latitude [°]	-61	56	12	35	-46	-7	-7	49	-29
longitude [°]	14	311	46	11	34	319	319	301	14
tilt [°]	35	65	50	5	35	-65	-65	-86	-10
hit/miss	miss	miss	miss	miss	miss	miss	miss	miss	hit
Conclusion:	miss	clear miss	likely miss	likely hit	miss	likely hit	clear miss	clear hit	
3D DBM runs: input and results for arrival time and speed at 1AU									
speed [km/s]	N/A	N/A	N/A	1187	N/A	518	N/A	N/A	637
radius@21.5Rs	N/A	N/A	N/A	4.1	N/A	5.4	N/A	N/A	9.8
density ratio	N/A	N/A	N/A	4	N/A	2	N/A	N/A	2
γ [1e-7km-1]	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.25	N/A	0.34	N/A	N/A	0.19
w [km/s]	N/A	N/A	N/A	350	N/A	350	N/A	N/A	430
FR TT [h]	N/A	N/A	N/A	63	N/A	94.2	N/A	N/A	
FR v [km/s]	N/A	N/A	N/A	485	N/A	415	N/A	N/A	
FR arrival	N/A	N/A	N/A	Nov-05 23:00	N/A	Dec-02 00:44	N/A	N/A	
shock	N/A	N/A	N/A	Nov-05 13:00	N/A	Dec-01 14:44	N/A	N/A	

Notes. The date is for the year 2023. Values marked with * are those where the full error range could not be applied, as e.g., it would mean that the aspect ratio is larger than 1 which is physically not meaningful, or that lon/lat goes too far away from the apex. The 3D DBM runs were performed using unaltered input from GCS results for rotation#2, but for CME1.4 adapted within the derived GCS errors to generate a flank hit (lat=25, tilt=-35) from which arrival time and speed could be obtained.